

PERSONALITY and DESIGN

The Intuitive Design Model

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Abstract: This project investigates the relationships of personality attributes on design choices. Specifically, this study investigates the correlations between individual personality types and the design characteristics that motivate each personality type. The outcome would be a design model based on individual personalities, as opposed to demographics or group behavior, a model for intuitive design.

Keywords: Personality and Design, Intuitive Design, Personality Types.

1. Introduction

Designers are not psychologists but they share similar objectives, which is to predict human behavior. A good designer needs to be able to “profile” their target market in order to determine what their market really wants or needs, typically without information or with conflicting information about their target market. The concept of using personality type in design goes to the core of target market preferences and motivation. Why do we want what we want and why do we buy what we buy?

This project is part of ongoing research to investigate the relationship of personality attributes on design choices. The study was conceived to develop a theory based on the connections between individual personality types and the design characteristics that motivate these personality types. An assumption is made, based on a psychological model, that within each personality type there are distinct behavior patterns and motivations attributable to each type. Because of these distinct behavior patterns, each type should have distinct design preferences. If a correlation can be established, a design model could be made based on these personality types and their core motivations. The outcome would set the base for a theory of intuitive design, a step beyond emotional design. Emotional Design describes how the meanings of products affect the users of products, love, hate, apathy,

connection, etc. Intuitive design could provide the reason behind those meanings and how to duplicate them on a relatively consistent basis. Essentially, it is the why we do what we do.

2. Precedent Design Models

Before intuitive design can be clearly defined, other models of design must first be addressed. These models can be and have been exclusive but I view them as a linear evolution in design thinking. Unfortunately, these models cannot be fully defined in the scope of this paper, but some basic definitions must be presented before intuitive design can be discussed.

The first model is *user-driven design*. At its most basic level, designers who use this model ask the user what he or she wants and they design a product based on the user's response. This is the most primary design model and the one that is most logical. This model provides the base for focus groups as well as mass customization. Currently, most design companies focus on understanding emerging user wants and needs, which they utilize in the development of user products that ideally provide the customer with a value that no competitor can match.¹ A common belief (and it may be so) is that the most successful companies are able to provide any choice that a user may want (e.g., the advent of mass customization). An issue arises with user-driven design in that many times users define their needs and wants based on current information. If a company tests a breakthrough change in meaning by relying on a typical focus group, people will search for what they already know.² They make their decisions on what is, not what could be. If innovation was left solely to focus groups, little progress in design would be made.

The second model is *user-centered design* or behavioral design. Behavioral designers observe their target market and design products based on behavioral observations of these markets. This model is based on the assumption that a user may or may not know what they want or need but observations of the user's behavior should lead to a desired design product. It is the analysis of the actions of the user, through the interpretation of the designer, that a design is created. This is an important step in design, because often users' perceptions of needs will conflict with their actual behavior.³ Observing the behavior of the user is also beneficial in learning which behaviors are learned behavior patterns or innate behaviors. Don Norman described these behaviors as levels of processing in *Emotional Design: Why We Love (or Hate) Everyday things*. The Reflective and Behavioral Levels would be considered the learned behaviors, with the Reflective being the highest level or contemplative level of thought and the Behavioral as the part of the brain that controls everyday behavior.⁴ The Visceral Level would control the innate or instinctual behavior. It is this level of visceral thought that starts to form the basis of intuitive design.

In the first model the designer asks what is to be designed. In the second model a designer observes user behavior and then provides a solution to a "perceived" need. Neither of these models guarantees a successful design. As Don Norman stated, "designing for the whims of fashion is tricky."⁵ Sometimes a consumer does not know what he or she needs. Sometimes, even if the consumer has a real need, they may not identify with that need or may not want a particular product (even if it is a perfectly functional design). If we look at the problem from the point of view of innovation, the observation of users will probably lead to an "incremental" attitude

towards innovation, while the real turning point for companies in a competitive market is the capability to generate “breakthrough” innovation.

The third model and probably the most contemporary model is *emotional design*. Emotional design has obvious appeal. Don Norman stated:

“Emotions are inseparable from and a necessary part of cognition. Everything we do, everything we think is tinged with emotion, much of it subconscious. In turn, our emotions change the way we think, and serve as constant guides to appropriate behavior, steering us away from the bad, guiding us toward the good.”⁶

If a designer asks what is wanted, what is needed, and also adds an emotional attachment it would potentially create a better design with this additional layer to the original product design. If a designer can create emotional appeal, then a consumer is more likely to form an attachment to the product and is also more likely to buy it. Emotional design is not about including “love;” it is about designing products with which consumers identify or form emotional attachments.

What is emotional design and how do you do it? The “what is emotional design” is relatively self-explanatory. The “how do you do it”, is the hard part and a concept that is mostly ignored. When emotional design occurs it is easy to spot. How to replicate this phenomenon is the issue. For the sake of argument, a user might as well ask a designer to include love. This is the problem with emotional design. Emotions by their very nature are not easily predictable or measurable. Different people will not feel the exact same emotion, consistently, to the same stimulus. Furthermore, an individual will not feel the same emotion, consistently, to the same stimulus on separate occasions. Emotions alone are not reliable. To evoke an emotion, a product needs somehow have meaning, particularly one with which a consumer can strongly identify. People do not buy products but meanings. As Krippendorff puts it:

“Looking back, Industrial design has always been concerned with what industrial artifacts mean. All schools, all movements, all philosophies, however short lived or ill-conceived they may appear to us now, can be characterized by their particular approach to making sense of material culture.”⁷

It is from this question of “how does a designer attach a meaning?” that intuitive design takes form. A designer needs to understand what generates the emotions that provide the attachment or in some cases the revulsion of some products. More specifically why do different groups of people have different meanings to the same products? The answer lies within the personalities of these individuals.

3. Intuitive Design

If emotions cannot be measured as a design trait, then what is the next step in the evolution of design? This is one of the questions that begins the discussion of Intuitive Design. The designing of products that have personal meaning with which people can identify. What are these meanings and why are they so different to each person? One can look at “meaning” as the vehicle to the emotion. If that analogy holds, then it is intuition influenced by personality that drives this vehicle.

The intuitive design theory, as proposed, is based on three factors; a personality model(the Enneagram model), Instinctual Variants and Design Motivators, all of which will be discussed further. However, a brief definition of Design Motivators would be those characteristics of design, as well as behaviors that motivate design identification and individual meaning within design. These motivators can be directly taken from the psychological characteristics of the personality types as well as other factors that cannot be as easily discerned. The assumptions for this theory are that there are distinct personality types and that there are core characteristics or design motivators that each personality has and values as more highly important. If these qualities can be identified and correlated then a designer can more intelligently design a product or service based on individual personality traits. Furthermore a designer, or company, can better understand how to provide meaning and attachment to what would seem to be widely different lifestyle markets.

4. Previous Research

A similar concept was proposed in a study by Michael Goatman from the University of Hertfordshire, UK (Emotion and Design, 2000)⁸. Goatman used the Myers-Briggs Type Indicator (MBTI) personality test and six garden drawings (each exhibiting different abstract designs) to examine if MBTI personality types correlated with design preferences. The intended outcome was a computer interface application based on the design process.

The results of this study were limited. Although there were some relationships shown to some personality characteristics, nothing conclusive was demonstrated. The limitations of the Hertfordshire project were due to a number of factors . Firstly, the sample size was too small for the number of variables investigated and the population was too homogeneous for statistical purposes. Secondly, the MBTI was not an optimal test for the study because it measures the process of HOW decisions are made not WHY those decisions are made. It is important to note that rudimentary correlations were found even in this limited study.

5. Personality Models

5.1. Current Personality Models

The more prevalent personality models currently used in psychology and the business and marketing fields are the OCEAN, the Luscher Color Test, and the Myers-Briggs Type Indicator. Each of these models has good validity but are not well suited for this project. The OCEAN (also known as the Big Five) is too broad to accurately classify base personalities. The Luscher Color Test does not classify personality, but instead provides insight into how an individual is perceived in the world as opposed to how that individual perceives themselves. The Myers-Briggs, based on theories of Carl Jung and the most commonly used, measures how decisions are made not why they are made.

5.2. The Enneagram Personality Model

The Enneagram personality model developed by Don Richard Riso and Russ Hudson , instead of the MBTI, provides the basic personality model for intuitive design. This is the first time that the Enneagram has been used

to correlate design and personality types. Furthermore, Don Riso, one of the co-developers of the Enneagram model, is advising on this project. The Enneagram Model is a more ideal categorization of personality for this type of study, as it is a measurement of personality-based motivation, It is intended to measure the “why” in decision making.

The validity of the Enneagram model has been demonstrated by independent researchers at SHL (2004). After a year of testing, Dr. David Bartram found that the nine personality types of the Enneagram are "real and objective" and that they stand on a par psychometrically with the Myers-Briggs system, the Big Five, and other well-known accepted psychological systems.⁹ The SHL study further concluded that 73% of people were correctly assigned to their types on the basis of the closest fitting profile. A further 13% had their correct type as the second smallest distance and overall, 94% had their correct type as the first, the second or the third smallest distance between their profile and the prototypical profile.¹⁰

Although the Enneagram has correlations to Jungian and Freudian typologies, the Enneagram does not use these categorizations as its basis for typology. The Enneagram is based on nine archetypal types, defined as such, for its classification of personality. The types with their core fixation (highlighted) are:

- 1 THE REFORMER The Rational, Idealistic Type: Principled, Purposeful, Self-Controlled, and Perfectionistic
- **Resentment**
- 2 THE HELPER The Caring, Interpersonal Type: Demonstrative, Generous, People-Pleasing, and Possessive
- **Pride**
- 3 THE ACHIEVER The Success-Oriented, Pragmatic Type: Adaptive, Excelling, Driven, and Image-Conscious
- **Deceit**
- 4 THE INDIVIDUALIST The Sensitive, Withdrawn Type: Expressive, Dramatic, Self-Absorbed, and Temperamental
- **Envy**
- 5 THE INVESTIGATOR The Intense, Cerebral Type: Perceptive, Innovative, Secretive, and Isolated
- **Avarice**
- 6 THE LOYALIST The Committed, Security-Oriented Type: Engaging, Responsible, Anxious, and Suspicious
- **Faithlessness**
- 7 THE ENTHUSIAST The Busy, Fun-Loving Type: Spontaneous, Versatile, Distractible, and Scattered
- **Gluttony**
- 8 THE CHALLENGER The Powerful, Dominating Type: Self-Confident, Decisive, Willful, and Confrontational
- **Lust**
- 9 THE PEACEMAKER The Easygoing, Self-Effacing Type: Receptive, Reassuring, Agreeable, and Complacent
- **Sloth**

A very brief introduction to the Enneagram is that it is a dialectical system, and as such it can be used to analyze different aspects of human nature dialectically. The Enneagram can be thought of as an arrangement of three Triads containing three different personality types. Each Triad is a dialectic of the problem of that triad. In each triad, one type has overdeveloped the characteristic faculty of the Triad, another has underdeveloped the faculty, and a third is most out of touch with the faculty.¹¹ The Feeling Triad consists of Types 2,3 and 4; The Thinking Triad, types 5,6 and 7; and The Instinctual Triad includes types 8,9 and 1. A more complete explanation of the Enneagram system can be found in *Personality Types: using the Enneagram for Self-discovery* by Don Riso and Russ Hudson.

6. Instinctual Variants

The second component to intuitive design are the Instinctual Variants (IV). The Instinctual Variants are based on three primary instincts that motivate behavior: *the Self-Preservation Instinct, the Social Instinct, and the Sexual Instinct*. Thus each Enneagram type has variations based on the three possible dominant instincts.¹²

- *The Self-Preservation Variant* – preoccupation with getting and maintaining physical safety and comfort.
- *The Social Variant* – preoccupation with being accepted and connected in the world.
- *The Sexual Variant* – preoccupation with attraction to energy and stimulation of energy.¹³

The Instinctual Variants help explain the subtle differences within each of the nine personality types. They are a hierarchy of what motivates each individual of each type. For example, a self-preservation variant would be more concerned with his or her surroundings and comfort level than a social variant of the same type, who would respond to interpersonal relations more than basic needs.

7. Design Motivators

The last component of intuitive design are the Design Motivators. As defined before, these are the characteristics of a design with which an individual identifies. They could include but are not limited to, aesthetic, spatial and functional attributes, as well as, behaviors of the individual. Many Design Motivators are unknown and the possibilities could be limitless. What can be shown within this introduction to intuitive theory is the relationships of how each personality type responds to base Design Motivators and also how, when using these motivators, each personality, or market, overlaps with other seemingly unrelated markets. However, a better understanding of what comprises the Design Motivators needs to be attained before practical examples are discussed.

7.1. Motivators based on personality characteristics (control group)

The Motivators based on the personality characteristics are the direct relationships between the attributes of each personality and how these attributes translate into design language. This group of Motivators would become in empirical terms the control group, i.e. each personality type should correlate to its own list of Motivators. These motivators were determined by myself, Don Riso and Katy Taylor, both of The Enneagram Institute.

An example of this correlation would be:

Type One – The Reformer

<u>Personality Traits</u>	<u>Design Correlation</u>
Organizing	Cleanness of Design
Clarity	Simple yet sophisticated
Right alignment Precision	Elegance
Precision	Balance
Symmetry	Symmetry
	Trend Aware
	Functional

7.2. Blue Sky Research – Alessandro Deserti

Another form of Design Motivator is exemplified by the Blue Sky Research project conducted by Alessandro Deserti of the Politecnico di Milano. Blue Sky is a categorization of current design styling into groups of products exhibiting similar characteristics. It is meant to be used to drive the design process with motifs of inspiration, to balance the use of technical requirements as a mean to address the development of design solutions. In the current year, the research focalized on terms like Soft, Deconstruction, Origami, Labyrinth, Interlace, Pixel, Ultra-light, Patchwork, Organics, and Wireframe, developing sets of visual textures for each category. The basic idea behind Blue-Sky Research is that if we want to be able to free our minds from constraints, we have to explore some references in search of sources of inspiration. For example, if we want to design a new piece of furniture and keep on looking at other pieces of furniture, we will never be able to find a strong innovation pathway.¹⁴

7.3. Free Design Motivators

The Free Design Motivators are, for lack of a better explanation, everything else. These are the characteristics of design to which people attach meaning that cannot be explained or defined by the personality system or abstract textural verbiage. The list of these motivators is essentially limitless. There will always be anomalies and outliers of Free Motivators if enough consumers are analyzed. However an attempt should be made to define the most common, as this would provide for designers a starting point in the design process. This is the area of intuitive design that crosses over to user-driven design. Individuals must be asked why they like what they like. From these responses, patterns of behavior and preference should form along the individual personality types.

Preliminary examples of some Free Design Motivators would be: Comfortable, Color, Contrasting, Natural/istic, Soft, Modern/ity, Simple, Form, Materiality, Unique, Clean, Curvilinear, Lightness, Warm, Open, and Linear. An argument can be made that some of the Free Motivators among personalities are universal, culturally influenced or both. For example, comfort would appear to be universal to all personalities but the importance

would vary among each of the types. Furthermore, each society has a differing view on the definition of comfort. An adage in the furniture industry is that Europeans sit “on” their sofas while Americans sit “in” their sofas. This is an important distinction if you are designing for a specific regional market. So it is possible that Free Design Motivators are more culturally dependent than those Motivators defined by the personality system.

8. Practical Application

At its most basic level, intuitive design is a method to profile target markets. It replaces the idea that target markets are demographics based on age and income. Instead, intuitive design views the markets from a psychological standpoint. Personalities remain unchanged regardless of income and age. Ultimately it is the personality of the users that will determine the meanings and the successes of the products. Furthermore, it allows a designer to design not just for one personality market but for multiple personality markets if the interrelationship of those types is understood. The next two figures show how one product can be designed successfully for more than one personality type and why that product appeals to those personalities.

Fig. 1 The “BMW” Example

In the first example (fig.1), the “BMW” example, shows the market for a high end sports car. This figure displays three similar personality types, but each with different motivations. The 7 motivated by adventure or speed, the 3 by prestige and the 8 by power. Sports cars have certain qualities with which each of these types

identify. To design a successful sports car for all three, a designer would look at what these personalities have in common. Drift too far away from the center, and the target markets shift toward the individual types. This is the most straight forward example. Few would disagree that the ultimate design criteria for a sports car is “to make a statement” about the person behind the wheel.

Figure 2 displays a more complex system. The “iPod example” is not to analyze the success of Apple but to show the relationship between very different personality types and how to design for those differences. The types of 1, 3 and 4 from a design standpoint are at extremes of the spectrum from each other. The 3 is very trend aware, the 1 is trend neutral and the 4 is trend averse or anti-trend. How does one product appeal to the “in-crowd” as well as the “outsider”?

Fig. 2 The “iPod” Example

Apple was able to design around the core Motivators of “quality”, “elegance” and “styling” and then add additional meanings with which each of these types identify. The appeal for the 3 was that it was fashionable and “cool”, among other reasons. The Type 1 appreciated the iPod’s cleanliness of design and its simplicity. The attraction for the Type 4 was not only the personalization and sensory experience of the iPod, but that, when the iPod was introduced it was the alternative to everything else, unique.

The theory of intuitive design could also be expanded to more accurately predict the success or failure of trends within design. With trends, there are varying degrees of “buy-in”. A person could completely follow the latest trend, or more likely modify the trend to their tastes or level of acceptance. The complete or partial acceptances are likely based on personality traits. What characteristics of the trend that affect each person would also be determined by their personality? A successful trend would be one that would be accepted by multiple personality types to varying degrees. Whereas, a failed trend would only affect a few types or one type resulting in, a small or specific market.

9. The Outcome

The framework of intuitive design could be used to create a tool that designers could use to generate more intelligent designs as well as create a system that can be implemented by, not only design professionals, but corporations. As with any system, for it to be fully completed every part must be understood. A complete system of human behavior is virtually impossible. Through the understanding of the motivations of that behavior, as it relates to design, the next step in intelligent design can take place. The theory of intuitive design as defined does not supplant design but creates a roadmap for design. It is a redefining of target markets, away from a focus on the masses, but instead, toward that of the individual. The designer is still, and will always be, a driving creative force in the design.

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